

Dissipative Structures Emerging in an Abstract Representation of a Neural Network Satisfying Hebb's Hypothesis

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Abstract:

This study presents a mathematical model of the learning process satisfying Hebb's assumptions: i.e. given any external input, a system of interconnected elements must necessarily give rise to an appropriate pattern of stable spatiotemporal activity. The author, adopting this point of view, did not use the models that consider learning as a modification of specific interconnection coefficients; instead, he made use of the continuous mathematical models of morphogenesis, identifying learning with the process of the formation of a dissipative structure; i.e., of a stable non-equilibrium structure, which is formed from a state of homogeneous equilibrium,

as soon as certain parameters exceed specific critical values.

Keywords: *Hebb Model, Dissipative Structures, Neural Networks, Symmetry Breaking.*

Introduction

The learning activity is considered a structural type of transaction triggered by using the appropriate external stimulus and associated with acquiring new patterns of behavior (Caianiello, 1961; Guazzo, 2024a). Some key features emerge from this definition (Pessa, 1983):

- 1) learning requires a modification of the attainable 'structure of stable states';
- 2) a learning process cannot occur unless external stimuli of appropriate form and intensity intervene;
- 3) once learning has taken place, the new structure that has thus originated must resist external perturbations and must yet hold its layer even if conditions before the process are restored, i.e. it must possess its stability

4) there must be, both before and after the learning process, stable states towards which the behaviour must tend;

5) after the learning process, there must remain a mnemonic trace (retention of what has been learnt) that will orient future behaviour;

6) involvement in a learning process must be partly independent of external stimuli and partly induced by them.

The first approach towards defining a system model that shows the learning process development fulfilling such a requirement dates to Hebb's work (Hebb, 1949). The main characteristics of Hebb's model, as regards our objective, may be synthetized as follows:

- a. the behaviour can be identified with the activity patterns of a neural network.
- b. the learning process consists of the variation of neuronics interconnection coefficients.

c. the memory is the coefficient status at a given time.

d. the values of such coefficients tend to be stable states depending on the network parameters and the nature of the external stimuli (Guazzo, 1993).

Some works (Feigenbaum, 1983; Grossberg, 1974; Cohen & Grossberg, 1983) show that the attempts to construct an adequate model of the learning processes following Hebb's hypothesis clash very hard with mathematical problems. A possible solution to the problem can be found by using the continuous mathematical model of morphogenesis within self-organizing systems (Guazzo, 2024b). This way, the learning process will no longer be considered interconnection coefficient transactions. Still, it will be identified as the creating process of a dissipative structure (Prigogine & Nicolis, 1982), i.e. a stable non-homogeneous non-equilibrium structure, which forms from a pre-existing homogeneous equilibrium state as soon as specific parameters exceed the determined critical values. This satisfies the requisites exposed in points 1, 3 and 4. In contrast, for those exposed in points 2 and 6, it will be necessary to add the assumption that external stimuli can directly influence the values of the model parameters; the requirements of point 5 imply, on the other hand, that the formation of a dissipative structure, due to the formation of spontaneous symmetry breaking, gives rise to a long-range correlation, which can be considered as memory (Guazzo, 2024b; Ermentrout & Cowan, 1980a, 1980b; Oosovets, Ginzburg, Gurfinkel', Zenkov, Latash, Malkin, Mel'nichuk & Pasternak, 1983; Ricciardi & Umezawa, 1967).

In the following section, the mathematical model of the learning process will be presented, in which many of the intermediate steps will be omitted in favour of the main ones.

The Mathematical Model

The considerations in the previous section suggest that the coefficient of interneuron

facilitation depends on the frequency of impulse passage in that channel, which, in the one synaptic model, is given by:

$$\frac{dw}{dt} = r_w(Pv - w) \quad (1a)$$

$$\frac{dP}{dt} = r_p(wv - P) \quad (1b)$$

The one synaptic case is a minimal system consisting of a single receptor neuron controlling a single interneuron, in which neuron v excites neuron w via the synapse P : $v(t)$ is the rate of 'activity' of the receptor neuron and $w(t)$ the activity of the interneuron, and P is the synaptic strength, or 'coupling' of the connection, from v to w . The coupling can be considered the system's memory, while the activity represents the response to the stimulus conditioned by the memory. Due to the positive feedback implicit in Hebb's postulate, the more negligible coupling will tend to grow if the input is sustained and sufficiently large. (Easton & Gordon, 1984).

If we generalize the model to the case of a network containing two types of connections, excitatory and inhibitory, the average activity of these neurons is represented by two mathematical functions:

$$u(x,t) = \text{excitatory activity}$$

$$v(x,t) = \text{inhibitory activity}$$

the global form of the model equations for the one-dimensional case is (Wilson & Cowan, 1973):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = D_1 \frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta x^2} + F_e(\beta_{ee}u + \beta_{ie}v - Q_e) \\ \frac{\delta v}{\delta t} = D_2 \frac{\delta^2 v}{\delta x^2} + F_i(\beta_{ei}u + \beta_{ii}v - Q_i) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

where D_1 , and D_2 are the diffusion coefficients of the variables u and v , F_e e F_i are threshold functions, β_{ee} , β_{ie} , β_{ei} , β_{ii} are variable coefficients and Q_e and Q_i represent the threshold.

In the case of the excitatory population alone, this will be the case:

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = D \frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta x^2} + F(\beta u - Q) \quad (3)$$

from which:

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = D \frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta x^2} + \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{\pi}(\beta u - Q) \quad (4)$$

by putting

$$\frac{1}{2} - \frac{Q}{\pi} = S \quad (5)$$

Equation (3) becomes:

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = D \frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \beta u + S \quad (6)$$

Considering:

$$P = \beta; \quad r = r_p; \quad v \sim u; \quad w \sim u; \quad \frac{d\beta}{dt} = r(u^2 - \beta)$$

System (2) becomes:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = D_1 \frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta x^2} + \frac{1}{\pi} \beta u + S \\ \frac{\delta v}{\delta t} = D_2 \frac{\delta^2 v}{\delta x^2} + r u^2 - r \beta \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

System (2) describes a self-organization process; therefore, a non-homogeneous

dissipative structure will appear when some parameters overcome “thresholds”. The equilibrium points of such a system can be found by using standard procedures):

$$\alpha_0 = -\sqrt[3]{\pi S} \quad (8.a)$$

$$\beta_0 = \sqrt[3]{(\pi S)^2} \quad (8.b)$$

To analyze the stability of the equilibrium points, we must linearize system (2) in the neighbours of those points.

Therefore let (Pessa, 1983):

$$u = u_0 + \xi \quad (9.a)$$

$$\beta = \beta_0 + \eta \quad (9.b)$$

By replacing (9.a) and (9.b) in the system (2) and neglecting exponential terms of ξ , η overcoming the first order, we have:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta \xi}{\delta t} = D_1 \frac{\delta^2 \xi}{\delta x^2} + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi} \xi + \frac{u_0}{\pi} \eta \\ \frac{\delta \eta}{\delta t} = D_2 \frac{\delta^2 \eta}{\delta x^2} + 2u_0 r \xi - r \eta \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

If we assume now that the solution has the following form:

$$\xi = c_1 e^{\lambda t} k x \quad (11.a)$$

$$\eta = c_2 e^{\lambda t} k x \quad (11.b)$$

And we replace (11.a) and (11.b) within system (10), we have:

$$\begin{cases} \left(-K^2 D_1 - \lambda + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi}\right) C_1 + \frac{u_0}{\pi} C_2 = 0 \\ 2u_0 r C_1 + (-r - K^2 D_2 - \lambda) C_2 = 0 \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

To have no null solutions in the system (6), the determinant of the system coefficient matrix must be equal to zero.

Solving to λ we have the relation (Guazzo, 2024b):

$$\lambda^2 - \lambda \left(-K^2 D_1 + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi} - K^2 D_2 - r\right) + \left(-K^2 D_1 + \frac{\beta_0}{\pi}\right) (-r - K^2 D_2) + \frac{2\alpha^2 r}{\pi} = 0 \quad (13)$$

The solution of (13), considered as a λ -equation, is stable if both roots λ have a negative real part. The critical point appears when either the known term is equal to zero or the coefficient of the λ -term is equal to zero.

Let us now suppose that one of the values λ is positive and assume:

$$r - r_0 = \gamma_1 \varepsilon + \gamma_2 \varepsilon^2 + \dots \quad (14)$$

where r_0 is the critical value of the parameter and ε is a small parameter.

Furthermore, let us assume that:

$$\xi = \varepsilon \xi_0 + \varepsilon^2 \xi_1 + \varepsilon^3 \xi_2 + \dots \quad (15.a)$$

$$\eta = \varepsilon \eta_0 + \varepsilon^2 \eta_1 + \varepsilon^3 \eta_2 + \dots \quad (15.b)$$

By replacing (14), (15.a) and (15.b) within the system (10) and making equal terms of the same order in ε , we obtain an infinite system of the equation of the following type:

$$\text{at } 1 - st \varepsilon - \text{order: } L_1(\xi, \eta) = Q_1(\xi, \eta) \quad (16.a)$$

$$\text{at } 2 - st \varepsilon - \text{order: } L_2(\xi, \eta) = Q_2(\xi, \eta) \quad (16.b)$$

If the operator $L_1(\xi, \eta)$ is equal to the system (10) with linear terms and $Q_1(\xi, \eta) = 0$, then it is possible to impose the following condition of solvability:

$$\int_0^l (\xi_0 R_1 + \eta_0 R_2) dx = 0 \quad (17)$$

where l is the length of the one-dimensional neural network.

We have an equation by developing the integral, where ξ_0 and η_0 it is known γ_1 .

If $\gamma_1 > 0$, then the dissipative structure is stable.

If $\gamma_1 < 0$, the dissipative structure is unstable.

Therefore, the dissipative structure form is:

$$\xi = \xi_0 + \left(\frac{r-r_0}{\gamma_1}\right) \xi_1 \quad (18.a)$$

$$\eta = \eta_0 + \left(\frac{r-r_0}{\gamma_1}\right) \eta_1 \quad (18.b)$$

where ξ_1 and η_1 are determined by resolving with approximation method the system of ε^2 -order.

If the system (2) does not depend on x , then it assumes the form:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = \frac{1}{\pi} \beta u + S \\ \frac{\delta \beta}{\delta t} = r u^2 + r \beta \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

Therefore, by deriving the first equation, we have:

$$\frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta t^2} - \frac{\pi}{u^2} \left(\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} \right)^2 + \left(-\frac{\pi S}{u} + r \right) \frac{\delta u}{\delta t} - \frac{ru^3}{\pi} - \frac{\pi S^2}{u^2} - rS + S^2 = 0 \quad (20)$$

By approximation of (20) for small new values of u , we have:

$$\frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta t^2} - \frac{\pi}{u^2} \left(\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} \right)^2 - \frac{\pi S}{u} \frac{\delta u}{\delta t} - \frac{ru^3}{\pi} - \frac{\pi S^2}{u^2} - rS + S^2 = 0 \quad (21)$$

where:

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = w(u) \quad (22.a)$$

$$\frac{\delta^2 u}{\delta t^2} = \frac{\delta w}{\delta u} \frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = w \frac{\delta w}{\delta u} \quad (22.b)$$

from which:

$$w \frac{\delta w}{\delta u} - \frac{\pi}{u^2} w^2 - \pi S \frac{w}{u} - \frac{\pi S}{u^2} = 0 \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\delta w}{\delta u} - \frac{\pi w}{u^2} - \frac{\pi S}{u} - \frac{\pi S}{u^2 w} = 0 \quad (24)$$

and by approximation of (20) for great new values of w , we have the linear equation:

$$\frac{\delta w}{\delta u} - \frac{\pi}{u^2} w = \frac{\pi S}{u} \quad (25)$$

from which:

$$w = \exp\left(-\frac{1}{u}\right) \left[\int \frac{\pi S}{u} \exp\left(\frac{1}{u}\right) \delta u + C \right] \quad (26)$$

$$\frac{\delta u}{\delta t} = e\left(-\frac{1}{u}\right) \left[Ei\left(\frac{1}{u}\right) + C \right] \quad (27)$$

where if u is very small, $\frac{1}{u}$ it is large, and one can find asymptotic developments $Ei\left(\frac{1}{u}\right)$, obtaining the approximate value of u by solving the equation:

$$\lambda^2 + \left(r - \frac{1}{u_0}\right) \lambda - \left(\frac{r}{\pi} 3u_0^2 - \frac{2\pi S^2}{u_0^3}\right) = 0 \quad (28)$$

From (28), the dissipative structure is unstable at a solution u_0 .

Conclusions

This work shows that it is possible to think of a temporal or spatial dissipative structure for critical values of the parameter. This implies that for appropriate values of r , it is impossible to have a homogeneous network and then assume the morphogenetic agent's rules.

Network connectivity can be automatically determined by dynamic evolution (Grossberg, 1980).

Moreover, some consequences can be derived from this model that could be subject to further experimental verification:

- 1) A learning process can only take place if the learning system, in the absence of external stimuli, is capable of a self-organizing process;
- 2) A learning process does not occur if the external stimuli do not exceed a certain critical value in intensity, but values that are too high or too low produce inactivity in the system or make it chaotic;
- 3) No learning is possible if there are not two types of internal activity, one excitatory and the other inhibitory, which interact reciprocally non-linearly.

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